

1 - Negative effect
2 - Neutral effect
3- Positive effect

3 - mostly outside of the park
2- partially inside of the park
1- mostly inside of the park

LSMP - licenced fishers
S - All the others

Source	Author	Common Name	Species	MPA effect	Life Cycle	Importance	Note
https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2013.05.004 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2015.07.020	Abecasis et al. 2013 Batista et al. 2015	Choco	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	2	2	LSMP	Low site fidelity and large movements. Increase of catches after implementation
https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4653 https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.3577 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2015.07.020	Sousa et al. 2018 Ramirez et al. 2021 Batista et al. 2015	Linguado	<i>Solea spp.</i>	1	1	LSMP	It is more abundant in the FPA, increased only size. Reduced catches
https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4654	Sousa et al. 2018	Raia	<i>Raja clavata</i> <i>Raja undulata</i> <i>Torpedo torpedo</i>	3	1	LSMP	General positive effect
https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4655 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106877	Sousa et al. 2018 Priester et al. 2021	Azevia	<i>Microchirus azevia</i>	3	1	LSMP	Indicator specie. Very positive response. High abundance
https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4656	Sousa et al. 2018	Salmonete	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	3	2	LSMP	General positive effect
http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.seares.2013.02.004	Henriques et al. 2013	Sargo	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	3	1	LSMP	General positive effect
http://dx.doi.org/10.3354/meps11054 http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.seares.2013.02.004	Abecasis et al. 2015 Henriques et al. 2013	Sargo	<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	3	1	LSMP	Positive effect
https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.3577	Ramirez et al. 2021	Dourada (espanhola)	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	2	2	LSMP	Increase in abundance and biomass but statistically not significant.
https://sapientia.ualg.pt/bitstream/10400.1/6073/1/Thesis_BHC_FINAL_4Julho2013_v3.pdf#page=39 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2015.07.020	Horta e Costa 2013 Batista et al. 2015	Polvo	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	3	1	LSMP, S	Increase in catches. showed the largest increase in biomass proportionally, suggesting a larger individuals inside the reserve
https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=388341159002	Stratoudakis et al. 2015	Lula	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	1	3	LSMP	The CPUE in 2013 was lower than before implementation
https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=388341159002	Stratoudakis et al. 2015	Pescada	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	3	3	LSMP, S	Increase probably due to conservation but mostly by the restoration of the Iberic stock
https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/fog.12269	Klein et al. 2018	Carapau	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	2	3	S	LSMP as a nursery for <i>T. trachurus</i> for post-larval and early juvenile.

https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2020.105785	Correia et al. 2021	Cavala	<i>Scomber colias</i>	?	3	S	Registered high mobility through heterogenic waters. High abundance.
https://doi.org/10.1007/s11852-014-0336-x https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2006.08.020	Cunha et al. 2014 Borges et al. 2007	Sardinha	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	2	3	S	Fish larvae close to the reefs. One of the most abundant.
http://dx.doi.org/10.1051/alr/2013061	Farias et al. 2013	Peixe-espada preto	<i>Aphanopus carbo</i>	2	3	S	No relevance.